

Excellent chemoselective synthesis of α,β -unsaturated ester moiety in introducing side chain in coumarin

Nitai Chand Sinha

Department of Chemistry, Sarat Centenary College, Dhaniakhali-712 302, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

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Abstract : Organomagnesium reagents failed to divulge any degree of chemoselectivity towards on 7-methoxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl methyl ketone **1** and 7-methoxy-4-methyl-8-formylcoumarin **2** but the carbanion triethyl phosphonoester shows excellent chemoselectivity together with high stereoselectivity during the synthesis of β -coumarinylacrylates **13**, **14** and β -coumarinylcrotonates **15** and **16**.

Keywords : Coumarin, chemoselective synthesis, unsaturated ester, side chain.

Introduction

Coumarins bearing various types of side chain at position 8 constitute well defined family having vast members of such phytochemicals and are enlisted with other diversified natural products¹⁻³. It has been revealed from the literature that allyl types of side chain can easily be developed by applying Claisen rearrangement⁴. This prompted us to undertake a systematic investigation in order to develop a new C-C side chain at position 8 by exploiting well known organic reactions, such as Grignard reaction, Edsworth-Emmons reaction towards the electrophilic centre of carbonyl functionality at position 8 of coumarin. Organomagnesium, organophosphorous reagents find almost routine use due to their high degree of chemoselectivity towards the electrophilic centre. In order to determine the chemoselectivity⁶ of such reagents and also to develop new C-C side chain, 7-methoxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl methyl ketone **1** and 7-methoxy-4-methyl-8-formylcoumarin **2** were prepared as substrate⁷. The systematic investigation of Grignard reaction^{8,9} on **1** and **2** failed to produce any degree of chemoselectivity at all. The products isolated are 2,2-disubstituted chromene derivatives **4** to **12**. The high nucleophilic character and low chemoselective nature of Grignard reagent prompted us to carry out Wittig's type Edsworth-Emmons reaction using anions of triethyl phosphonoester^{10,11} which is well

known for high chemoselective and fairly good nucleophilic character to develop C-C side chain at position 8. It has been observed that some new diastereoselective as well as chemoselective ethyl- β -(7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarinyl)-acrylate **13** and **14** and ethyl- β -(7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarinyl)-crotonate **15** and **16** were synthesised from **1** and **2** using anion of triethyl phosphonoacetate **17** and triethyl phosphonopropionate **18**. Thus the failure of Grignard reagents as chemoselective nature and excellent chemoselective as well as stereoselectivity of Edsworth-Emmons reaction were observed during the synthesis of α,β -unsaturated ester moiety in coumarins which constitute the subject of the present communication.

Experimental

Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. UV spectra were taken in ethanol in a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi 200 spectrophotometer. IR spectra in nujol mull when solid and when liquid on Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ on JEOL FX 100 machine using TMS as internal standard. ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Varian XL-400 spectrometer. Mass spectra of solid compounds were recorded on RMU 6L instruments operating at 60 eV.

Grignard reaction 1 and 2 with various alkyl and aryl magnesium halides : General procedure : The respective

Grignard reagents were prepared by dropwise addition of alkyl halide or aryl halide (9 mmol) with continuous stirring to magnesium turnings (10 mmol) in dry THF (50 ml). When the entire magnesium turning was dissolved, the clear solution of Grignard reagents thus prepared was added dropwise to a stirred solution of **1** (4.5 mmol) or **2** (4.5 mmol) in dry THF (100 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 h at room temperature and then refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, decomposed by 20% ice cold HCl and finally extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with saturated brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent afforded the crude products which on column chromatographic separation over silica gel afforded the products **3-7** from **1** and **8-12** from **2** together with starting material **1** and **2** respectively.

Reaction of 1 and 2 with the respective carbanions of triethyl phosphonoacetate 18 and triethyl phosphonopropionate 19. General procedure : A solution of sodium ethoxide (4.5 mmol) in dry absolute ethanol (10 ml) was cooled and to it respective triethyl phosphonoacetate and propionate (5.0 mmol) was added slowly with constant stirring at 0 °C for 10 min and allowed the solution to remain at room temperature for 10 min. The clear solution of **1** (4.5 mmol) or **2** (4.5 mmol) was added dropwise to the respective solution of **17** and **18** under perfectly

Table-1 (contd.)

9	42	95/0.1 mm	C ₈ H ₂₆ O ₃	77.14 (77.00)	9.28 (9.18)
10	47	72°	C ₂₁ H ₃₂ O ₃	75.70 (75.9)	9.6 (9.64)
11	76	150°	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₃	82.9 (82.9)	6.0 (6.1)
12	60	155°	C ₃₃ H ₃₂ O ₆	76.0 (75.9)	6.3 (6.2)
13	30	141	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₅	67.19 (67.23)	5.98 (5.96)
14	33	107-108	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅	68.30 (68.34)	6.29 (6.29)
15	62	130-131	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅	66.40 (66.60)	5.5 (5.55)
16	63	135-137	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₅	67.19 (67.0)	5.98 (5.90)

dry condition at 20 °C. Now the reaction mixtures were stirred for 4 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture thus obtained from **1** and **2** were poured into brine solution (200 ml) and extracted with ethylacetate. The organic layer was washed with brine and solvent was evaporated. The crude reaction products on column chromatographic separation over silica gel afforded **13** and **14** from **1** and **15** and **16** from **2** along with the respective starting materials **1** and **2**.

Table 1. Physical data of some new compounds

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p./b.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Elemental analysis (%)	
				Calcd./(Found)	
				C	H
3	30	70-75/1 mm	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂	78.7 (78.2)	8.1 (8.0)
4	48	100/2 mm	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₂	75.0 (74.7)	9.2 (9.0)
5	40	89°	C ₂₇ H ₃₂ O ₂	80.5 (79.4)	9.8 (9.5)
6	68	170°	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₃	83.0 (82.9)	6.3 (6.0)
7	60	146-147	C ₃₄ H ₃₂ O ₃	78.5 (78.3)	6.2 (6.0)
8	31	100-105/ 0.1 mm	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₃	72.58 (72.3)	8.06 (8.10)

- 3 R = Me, R¹ = MeC=CH₂
 4 R = Et, R¹ = MeC(OH)Et
 5 R = CHMe₂, R¹ = MeC=C(Me)₂
 6 R = Ph, R¹ = MeC(OH)Ph
 7 R = *p*-Anisyl, R¹ = *p*-Anisyl C=CH₃
 8 R = Me, R¹ = CH(OH)Me
 9 R = Et, R¹ = CH(OH)Et
 10 R = CHMe₂, R¹ = CH(OH)CMe₂
 11 R = Ph, R¹ = CH(OH)Ph
 12 R = *p*-Anisyl, R¹ = CH(OH) *anisyl-p*
 18 (EtO)₂-P-C-CO₂Et
 | |
 O Me

- 19 R = H, Me

- 20 R = H, Me

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The products isolated from Grignard reaction were subjected to UV and IR spectral studies. The compounds

3-12 exhibit absorption of 307 (log ϵ 3.84) to 304 (log ϵ 3.70) and 295 (log ϵ 3.67) to 262 (log ϵ 3.89). Comparative studies of UV spectra (Table 2) suggest that the compounds 3-12 turn out to be helpful to establish the presence benzopyran chromophores and carbonyl functionalities. ¹H NMR spectra of the compounds 4, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 are interesting and demand special discussion. These compounds contain an alcoholic -OH group which has been recorded as a singlet at comparatively down field (around δ 5.2) region. The singlet nature and downfield absorption of alcoholic -OH group may be explained by assuming that in such compounds intramolecular hydrogen bonding take place where oxygen of the pyran ring is involved. The said solid products gave expected mass fragmentation and are fully characterized. It should be mentioned in this connection that the substrates 1 and 2 have two electrophilic centres of which one is electron deficient keto or aldehyde functionality and the other is moderate electron deficient lactone carbonyl site. The hot carbanions of Grignard reagent attack both the lactone carbonyl as well as carbonyl site of 1 and 2 with the formation of 2,2-disubstituted chromene derivative 3 to 7 from 1 and 8-12 from 2 even such reagents are used in smaller amount. The failure of Grignard reagent during chemoselective synthesis of C-C side chain at position 8 prompted us to undertake successful investigation on coumarin derivative 1 and 2 with the respective carbanion of triethyl phosphonoacetate 17 and propionate 18 afforded some new ethyl- β -(7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarinyl)-crotonate 13 and 14 and ethyl- β -(7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarinyl)-acrylate 15 and 16 respectively. Going through the UV, IR and ¹H NMR data (Table 2) and comparison of Me and ¹H signals in ¹H NMR (Table 3), one may easily confirm the presence of 4-methyl-7-methoxycoumarin moiety and also α,β -unsaturated ester side chain at position 8. The configuration of olefinic double bond of unsaturated ester at position 1' be assigned *E* since ³*J* value of 1'-H and 2'-H is 17 Hz in ¹H NMR in 15. In compound 13, 2'-H and in compound 16 1'-H appeared at δ 5.04 and 7.90 as quintet, *J* 1 Hz and the olefinic double bond may be assigned *E*. Similarly in compound 14, 1'-Me and 2'-Me are anti to each other.

In order to get further data regarding the structural feature of α,β -unsaturated ester 13 to 16, ¹³C NMR studies were taken up and ¹³C splitting pattern (CH₃, 2⁰, 3⁰, quaternary) was established using resonance decoupled

Table 2. Relevant spectral data of some new compounds

Compd.	UV (λ_{\max} in cm^{-1})	IR (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1})	^1H NMR (CDCl_3/TMS) δ ppm	MS m/z rel int (%)
3	303 (3.73), 262 (3.67), 254 (3.62)	1598, 1497, 1485	6.97 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.35 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 6-H), 5.28 (2H, br.s, 2'-H), 4.85 (1H, q, J 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 3.77 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.17 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 4- CH_3), 1.96 (1H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 1'- CH_3), 1.20 (6H, s, two 2'- CH_3)	
4	305 (3.77), 262 (3.67)	3560, 1601, 1460	6.90 and 6.40 (each 1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H and 6-H), 5.04 (1H, s, -OH), 5.16 (1H, q, J 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 1.98 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 4- CH_3) 1.80-1.70 (4H, m, 2- CH_2CH_3), 1.64 (2H, s, 1'- CH_3) 1.64-1.18 (2H, br.m, - CH_2CH_3), 0.9-0.6 (9H, br.m, three CH_3)	
5	304 (3.76), 269 (3.54), 265 (3.58)	1601, 1495, 1485, 1460	6.9 and 6.34 (each 1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H and 6-H), 5.04 (1H, q, J 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.04 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 4- CH_3), 1.92 (2H, m, CHMe_2), 1.88 (6H, s, two 2'- CH_3), 1.46 (3H, s, 1'- CH_3), 0.95-0.89 (12H, m, four CH_3 of CHMe_2)	
6	307 (3.73), 264 (3.59)	3518, 1598, 1440	7.21-7.20 (7H, br.m, Ar-H), 7.01 (8H, br.m, Ar-H), 7.00 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.40 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 6-H), 5.63 (1H, s, OH), 5.23 (1H, q, J 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 3.52 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.10 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 4- CH_3), 1.9 (3H, s, 1'- CH_3)	448 (100), 433 (97.3), 432 (98), 415 (17.0), 371 (62.9), 370 (92.6), 335 (40.8), 327 (10), 251 (250)
7	306 (3.78), 264 (3.71), 256 (4.62)	1601, 1598, 1485	7.21-7.02 (7H, br.m, Ar-H), 6.77-6.72 (6H, br.m, Ar-H), 6.48 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 6-H), 5.80 (1H, br.s, 2'-H), 5.66 (br.s, 2'-H), 5.14 (1H, q, J 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.71 (6H, s, two - OCH_3), 3.64 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.08 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 4- CH_3)	520 (50.5), 505 (74.1), 413 (100), 399 (10.6), 269 (2.57), 255 (10.6), 241 (1.36), 240 (1.36)
8	360 (3.77), 262 (3.66)	3525, 1600, 1448	6.82 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.41 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 6-H), 5.25 (1H, s, OH), 4.98 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, 3-H), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.25 (1H s, 1'-H), 2.20 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 4- CH_3), 2.00 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 1'- CH_3), 1.40 (6H, s, 2'- CH_3)	
9	304 (3.79), 263 (3.68)	3528, 1601, 1466	6.89 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.35 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 6-H), 5.28 (1H, s, OH), 5.15 (1H, s, 3-H), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.15 (1H, t, J 10 Hz, 1'-H) 2.00 (3H, d, J 0.5 Hz, 4- CH_3), 1.18-1.14 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 1.10-0.85 (9H, m, J 8 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_3$)	

Note

Table-2 (contd.)

10	306 (3.86), 265 (3.67)	3540, 1601, 1498, 1460	6.90 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.35 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 6-H), 5.18 (1H, s, OH), 5.15 (1H, s, 3-H), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 2.25 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 10 Hz, 1'-H), 2.05 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 4-CH ₃), 2.02 (1H, m, <i>J</i> 5.5 Hz, 1'-CHMe ₂), 1.92 (2H, compl.m, 2-CHMe), 1.00-0.92 (18H, compl.m, 3-CHMe ₂)	
11	307 (3.73), 264 (3.59)	1601, 1598, 1460	7.21-7.05 (6H, br.m, Ar-H), 7.01-6.96 (9H, br.m, Ar-H), 6.90 and 6.84 (each 1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 5-H, 6-H), 5.18 (1H, s, OH), 5.16 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 3.76 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 2.12 (1H, s, 1'-H), 2.08 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 0.05 Hz, 4-CH ₃)	434 (90.0), 433 (80.0), 432 (82.0), 416 (73.2), 401 (13.0), 357 (98.0) 356 (100), 355 (41.0), 327 (450)
12	308 (3.69), 263 (3.60)	1600, 1595, 1460	7.24-7.20 (6H, br.m, Ar-H), 6.99 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.80-6.60 (7H, br.m, Ar-H), 5.20 (1H, s, OH), 5.18 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 3.76 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 3.58 (9H, s, 3-OCH ₃), 2.12 (1H, s, 1'-H), 2.08 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 4-CH ₃)	524 (70.5), 523 (100), 510 (99), 493 (24.5), 417 (94.0), 416 (13.0), 410 (32.5), 378 (54.5)
13	320 (4.24), 255 (4.00)	1722, 1700, 1598	7.34 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.72 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.00 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 5.04 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 1 Hz, 2'-H), 4.09 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 2.36 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 4-CH ₃), 2.52 (3H, s, 1'-CH ₃), 1.26 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃)	302 (100), 287 (12.2), 271 (50.5), 244 (12.7), 242 (50.5), 229 (90), 219 (51.5), 215 (40.4), 199 (14.0)
14	318 (4.15), 259 (3.89)	1718, 1688, 1610	7.67 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.26 and 6.67 (each 1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 5-H, 6-H), 4.10 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.74 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 2.48 (3H, s, 1'-CH ₃), 2.20 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 4-CH ₃), 1.90 (3H, s, 2'-CH ₃), 1.31 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃)	316 (34.4), 301 (9.8), 287 (12.2), 271 (50.8), 244 (100), 242 (50.8), 229 (37.0), 215 (12.5)
15	320 (4.05), 254 (4.04)	1703, 1680, 1608	7.96 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 18 Hz, 1'-H), 7.54 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz 5-H), 6.91 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 6-H), 6.57 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 18 Hz, 2'-H), 6.14 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, 3-H), 4.09 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.00 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 2.47 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 4-CH ₃), 1.37 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃)	288 (100), 287 (75.0), 260 (2.92), 259 (16.8), 243 (28.7), 229 (170), 215 (34.0)
16	318 (4.08), 258 (3.80)	1710, 1674, 1598	7.90 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 17 Hz, 1'-H), 7.70 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 3-H), 7.27 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 5-H), 6.64 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 6-H), 4.20 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 2.48 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 0.5 Hz, 4-CH ₃), 1.80 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 1 Hz, 2'-CH ₃), 1.20 (1H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, 2'-CO ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃)	302 (100), 274 (5.0), 260 (16.8), 229 (60.4), 20 (50.4), 189 (17.4)

Table 3. Comparison of methyl and H signal in ^1H NMR spectra

Compd.	Chemical shift (δ) with splitting pattern			
	1'-Me	2'-Me	1'-H	2'-H
13	2.52 (s)			5.04 (d)
14	2.58 (s)	1.90 (s)		
15			7.96 (d)	6.58 (d)
16		1.98 (d)	7.90 (d)	

technique¹² (Table 4). Thus all these observations prove that 1'-Me and 2'-Me in 14 or 1'-H and 2'-Me in 16 do not maintain close proximity in space and should be anti

Table 4. ^{13}C NMR spectra of some new compounds 13 to 16

Assignment of specific carbons	Chemical shifts (δ) for the compounds			
	13	14	15	16
C-2	157.9	157.5	159.9	157.2
C-3	111.9	116.5	117.4	116.6
C-4	149.0	149.6	149.8	149.6
C-5	124.0	125.0	125.5	124.8
C-6	105.9	105.0	112.0	105.7
C-7	159.1	157.8	160.4	157.4
C-8	115.9	115.8	115.2	115.9
C-9	136.0	135.9	136.0	135.8
C-10	118.5	116.4	118.0	118.8
Me-4	18.6	19.0	19.2	18.8
MeO-7	56.0	56.8	56.6	56.2
C-1'	135.0	135.8	132.2	131.8
C-2'	107.0	105.8	135.8	107.5
C-3'	168.3	168.5	167.0	168.0
C-4'	59.9	59.8	61.5	59.7
Me-1'	32.0	32.1		
Me-2'		11.5	14.5	14.5
Me-4'	14.1	14.6	14.1	13.6

in their relationship and thus the configuration of α,β -unsaturated side chain at position 8 must be *E* and the side chain is most likely out of plane with the aromatic system from the configurational point of view. Hence the preferred conformation of 14 as well as 16 may be represented as 19 and 20.

Thus it is interesting to note that the diastereoselectivity is distinctly in favour of thermodynamically more stable *E*-isomer of the 1'-olefinic double bond because the formation of intermediate betaine is reversible and this allows the formation of more stable stereoisomeric form of betaine in which the stabilizing group ethoxycarbonyl *trans* to the larger β -substituent. Thus an inter conversion to the more stable and more abundant isomeric form and *syn* elimination afforded *E*-isomer. Finally the above struc-

tures get complete support from mass spectral analysis¹⁵. The most important ion peaks for the fragments at particular *m/z* along with their relative intensity (%) are recorded for compounds 13 to 16 (Table 2).

Conclusion :

From the result and discussion it transpires that the carbanion of triethylphosphonoesters attack only the carbonyl group not the lactone carbonyl functionality. So the above reagents are excellent chemoselective along with high stereoselective in introducing side chain at position 8 in coumarins.

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References

- H. Fuher, T. R. Gobindachari and B. S. Joshi, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 8, 198.
- A. G. Gonzalez, R. Estavez and I. Jariaz, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, 10, 1621.
- J. Mann, "Secondary Metabolism", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1978, p. 155.
- W. R. Backer and C. M. Lothian, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 628.
- H. O. House, "Modern Synthetic Reaction", W. A. Benjamin, Inc, 2nd ed., 1972, pp. 635, 731.
- S. Warren, "Organic Synthesis : The Disconnection Approach", John Wiley & Sons., 1982, p. 34.
- R. A. Russel, J. P. Frye and W. L. Maldin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1442; J. Duff and E. Bill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1035.
- S. Barnes and M. T. Strong, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 839.
- C. A. Holmberg and M. Malmstrong, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1973, 27, 2023.
- J. Bantagy and R. Thomson, *Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 74, 87.
- B. J. Walker, "Organophosphorous Reagent in Organic Synthesis", Academic Press, New York, 1979, p. 155.
- J. K. M. Sanders and B. K. Hunter, "Modern NMR Spectroscopy", Oxford University Press, 2nd ed., 1993, p. 138.
- J. B. Stothers, "Carbon-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic Press, 1972.
- R. Benn and H. Gunthers, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1983, 22, 350.
- Q. N. Porter and J. Baldes, "Mass Spectroscopy of Heterocyclic Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970, pp. 147-168.